

Original article

A qualitative assessment of the impact of trichiasis surgery on quality of life of affected patients within Bauchi metropolis of Bauchi state, north-east, Nigeria

Hauwa Batah,¹ Funmilayo J. Oyediji,² Bala T. Rano,¹ Maji D Attalawo,¹ Maji D Attalawo.¹

¹Department of Ophthalmology, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, Bauchi State.

²Department of Ophthalmology, Jos University Teaching Hospital, Jos, Plateau State.

*Corresponding author: Hauwa Batah, Department of Ophthalmology, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, Bauchi State. Email: hauwabee84@gmail.com Tel No: 07063937497.

Abstract

Background: Trachoma is the leading infectious cause of blindness worldwide, and trichomatous trichiasis (TT) – the in-turning of eyelashes – causes persistent pain, photophobia, and progressive corneal damage, profoundly impairing quality of life. While surgical correction of TT is a cornerstone of the WHO-endorsed SAFE strategy for trachoma elimination, the subjective, lived-experience benefits of such surgery remain under-explored in many endemic settings, including northern Nigeria. This study therefore qualitatively explored the impact of TT surgery on the quality of life of affected individuals in Bauchi Metropolis, Bauchi State, Nigeria. **Materials and methods:** A qualitative research study that conducted focus group discussions (FGDs) in five out of the 12 wards of Bauchi Metropolis, which were selected by random sampling. It was conducted alongside a quantitative study of patients with trichiasis who benefited from a free surgical intervention provided by a non-governmental organisation (NGO) to support the global elimination of trachoma in Bauchi State. A total of 34 participants were recruited for the study. Each FGD had 6–8 purposively selected participants from each ward who agreed to participate. Informed consent was obtained from all participants. All FGDs were conducted in the Hausa language by a trained moderator, and participants' responses were recorded by two assistants at each discussion through written notes and audio recording. Each discussion lasted 60–90 minutes. Participants were asked open-ended questions and encouraged to respond freely; there were no right or wrong answers. The main aim was to gain in-depth insight into their experiences, with confidentiality maintained until data saturation was achieved (after the fourth FGD). Data were analysed through verbatim translation, transcription, familiarisation, coding, and theme identification. The findings were interpreted and reported using content analysis. **Result:** Trichiasis had a significant negative impact on participants' quality of life, affecting physical and social health, sense of security, ability to perform daily activities, independence, and capacity to care for families. Surgical intervention led to improvement in physical and social health, security, daily functioning, independence, and family care. Participants also had limited knowledge of the causes of trichiasis, other treatment options, and how it could lead to blindness; they were appropriately educated after each discussion. **Conclusion:** TT had a significant negative impact on quality of life, and surgical intervention led to significant improvement in quality of life among patients with TT in the Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State.

Keywords: Focus group discussion, Qualitative research, Quality of life, Trichomatous trichiasis, Trichiasis surgery.

Open Access article distribution in the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC by 4.0)

Copyright: The Author(s). 2025

ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20670042>

Date Submitted: 9th May 2026

Date Accepted: 2nd June 2026

Date Published Online: 12th June 2026

Cite this article as:

Hauwa Batah, Funmilayo J. Oyediji, Bala T. Rano, Maji D Attalawo. A Qualitative Assessment of the Impact of Trichiasis Surgery on Quality of Life of Affected Patients within Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State, North-East, Nigeria. *The Scholar J Health Scie* 2026; 2 (1): 325-331.

Introduction

Trachoma, a neglected tropical disease, is a leading cause of infectious blindness,^{1,2} which follows its cicatricial complication: trichomatous trichiasis (TT; hereafter referred to as "trichiasis" for brevity).² The World Health Organisation (WHO) advocates the SAFE strategy for its global elimination.³ Before causing blindness, trichiasis affects the quality of life of those affected, leading to physical suffering (eye pain, irritation, tearing, foreign body sensation),^{4,5} psychological distress (embarrassment, anxiety, low self-esteem),^{4,6} socio-economic consequences (loss of social status,

inability to work, reduced participation in religious and social activities, increased burden to families),⁶⁻⁸ and reduced overall well-being.⁸ Surgical intervention generally improves patient comfort and physical functioning, but direct qualitative data on broader quality of life outcomes remains limited and under-researched.⁸⁻¹⁰

Previously conducted studies on this topic (mostly quantitative) revealed significant physical, psychological, environmental, and social benefits for affected patients.^{7,11} The findings consistently show that surgery improves well-being and daily functioning, often even without vision improvement.^{8,12}

There is a lack of qualitative research specifically addressing the impact of trichiasis surgery on quality of life. Most studies were quantitative and conducted outside Nigeria;^{4-6,8,11,12} they do not provide in-depth knowledge about the lived experience of trichiasis. Moreover, these quantitative studies used validated questionnaires that were not specifically designed for patients with trichiasis. Qualitative research is valuable for capturing patient experiences, perceptions, and psychosocial impacts, revealing domains such as physical and social health, interpersonal relationships, and self-image—domains that quantitative measures may miss.

The aim of this research was to qualitatively assess the impact of trichiasis surgery on the quality of life (QoL) of affected patients in Bauchi metropolis, Bauchi State, Nigeria. The study was conducted to gather data on patients' experiences with trichiasis and the impact of surgical intervention. This is particularly relevant because Bauchi State had 19 out of its 20 local government areas (LGAs) with trichiasis prevalence above the WHO elimination target of <0.2%.¹³

Materials and Methods

Study setting and design

The study was conducted in the Bauchi metropolis, the state capital of Bauchi State, by a senior registrar in the Department of Ophthalmology, FUHSTHA, Katagum LGA (corresponding author). It was a research topic for her fellowship dissertation with the NPMCN during her residency programme at the National Eye Centre, Kaduna. The researcher had no prior relationship with the communities where the study took place, nor with the NGO offering free trichiasis surgical intervention in the State.

This was a qualitative research study conducted through focus group discussions (FGDs) in five of the twelve wards of the Bauchi metropolis, selected

using simple random sampling. It was done alongside a quantitative study assessing the impact of trichiasis surgery on health-related quality of life.¹⁶ The surgery was offered free of charge by an NGO within the state capital.

Ethical considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of the National Eye Centre, Kaduna. Administrative approval was obtained from the primary health care management board and from the Commonwealth Fund project (HANDS), which sponsored the free trichiasis surgery. Informed written consent was obtained from all participants by reading each consent form aloud in the presence of relatives who served as witnesses, after ensuring that the information was understood, and before signing.

Participant recruitment

A total of 34 participants (3 males, 31 females) aged 15 years and above were purposively selected with assistance from TT finders (community health workers trained to identify trichiasis cases) within each ward, who approached participants face-to-face. Inclusion criteria: residents of Bauchi metropolis, ability to understand Hausa, and absence of severe ocular or medical conditions. Purposive sampling yielded only three eligible males across all five wards, reflecting both the higher prevalence of trichiasis among females in this setting.¹⁵ and possibly lower willingness of males to participate in group discussions about an eye condition.

Focus group discussions

Five FGDs were conducted, with 6–8 participants per group, within the premises of the primary health centre (PHC) in each ward. Participants were seated comfortably in a circle away from relatives and friends. All FGDs were conducted in Hausa language by a trained moderator, and responses were recorded by two assistants using written notes and audio recording. Each FGD lasted 60–90 minutes. Participants were assigned serial numbers for anonymity. They were informed that open-ended questions had no right or wrong answers and that the goal was to gain in-depth insight into their experiences while living with TT. Serial discussions were conducted until data saturation was achieved. Data saturation was achieved after the fourth FGD, when no new codes or themes emerged; the fifth FGD confirmed existing themes without adding any novel insights. All FGDs were conducted **after** surgical intervention; therefore, participants' descriptions of

their pre-surgery experiences are retrospective. Time from surgery to FGD ranged from 2 to 10 months (mean 5.4 months).

Discussion guide

Participants were asked open-ended questions based on a discussion guide:

- What problems did you face when you had trichiasis? (Impact on QoL)
- Did trichiasis affect your sleep?
- What changes did you notice following surgery?
- What do you think causes trichiasis?
- What other treatments for trichiasis do you know?
- Do you think trichiasis can cause blindness, and if so, how?

Data analysis

Data from written notes and audio recordings were triangulated. Audio recordings were transcribed verbatim after translation into English, with a bilingual reviewer checking for accuracy. Non-verbal cues were included. Two independent coders performed content analysis: familiarisation, initial coding, codebook development, theme identification, and refinement. Disagreements in coding were resolved through systematic consensus dialogue, codebook adjustment, and standardisation. Member checking (returning transcripts to participants for correction) was not performed, nor were repeat FGDs conducted for confirmation; this is acknowledged as a limitation (see Discussion).

Education and distress protocol

After completing the FGD questions, participants were educated about trachoma as a neglected tropical disease, transmission, how cicatricial changes cause trichiasis, how it can lead to blindness if untreated, and treatment options. A trained counsellor was present at each FGD to support any participant experiencing distress due to discussion of discomfort, stigma, or possible blindness. No distress was recorded during the study.

Results

Demographic characteristics

Five FGDs were conducted across Bauchi metropolis with a total of 34 participants (3 males, 31 females). Table 1 shows the distribution by ward.

Table 1: Distribution of FGD participants

Ward	No. of females	No. of males	Total participants
Dawaki	7	1	8
Kangere/Tirwun	6	0	6
Birshi/Miri	5	1	6
Makama	6	1	7
Dandango/Yamrat	7	0	7
Total	31	3	34

Themes

Four main themes emerged (Table 2):
 A. Participants’ experiences while living with trichiasis
 B. Participants’ experiences following trichiasis surgery
 C. Participants’ knowledge about trichiasis
 D. Participants’ knowledge about trichiasis treatments

A. Participants’ experiences while living with trichiasis

Physical symptoms

Most participants reported eye redness, recurrent or persistent tearing, discharge, and varying degrees of discomfort. One participant stated: “I had recurrent pricking eye sensation, which felt like I had a grain of sand in my eye, which made me blink constantly” (R20). Another said, “The condition felt like someone was trying to cut my eyeball with a sharp knife persistently” (R2). Foreign body sensation, itching, blurred vision, double vision, photophobia, and frequent headaches were also reported (R2, R3, R4, R5, R8, R9, R10, R11, R14, R15, R22, R24, R25, R27).

However, one participant had no discomfort (e.g., pain, tearing, foreign-body sensation) but was found to have trichiasis when she escorted a friend to the PHC; she reported improved vision (blurring resolved) following surgery. A participant with under-correction also responded positively: “I was also told that I still have a few offending lashes in the operated eye, but I am still very happy because I am much better compared to before. Thank you” (R14).

Stigmatisation

Stigmatisation was more common among females than males. Male participants stated that they viewed trichiasis as a trial from God and therefore did not feel ashamed. Most females, however,

Table 2: FGDs Themes and subthemes

Theme	Subtheme	Definition	Representative quotes (examples)*
A. Participants' experiences while living with TT	1. Physical symptoms 2. Stigmatisation 3. Loss of independence 4. Search for cure & economic impact 5. Interference with family care 6. Effect on sleep	Physical problems; discomfort/shame; dependence on others; long search for solution & cost; inability to care for family; sleep disturbance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "pricking eye sensation, eye pains, redness" (R3, R8, R11, etc.) • "Yes I felt ashamed... children used to run away from me" (R14) • "I could not drive my motorcycle... affected his work too" (R19) • "Used medications... did not know how to remove lashes" (R3-R25) • "Tearing worsened while cooking... interfering with my ability to take care of my family" (R2,R3,R5) • "Yes, I used to remove it so that I can sleep well at night" (R13,R17,R22)
	1. Improved health 2. Improved independence, security, earning 3. Better ability to function & care for family	Better wellbeing; better earning; work better and care for family	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "I am fine now; all tearing resolved" (R1) • "I can now travel on my motorcycle for long distances" (R7,R8,R19) • "I can do my domestic chores freely now" (R3)
C. Participants' knowledge about TT	1. Knowledge on causes 2. Knowledge if TT causes blindness and how	What leads to trichiasis; can TT cause blindness and how	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Disease contracted by sharing eye pencils" (R3) • "Caused by dust and cold during harmattan" (R1,R25) • "Yes, because it scratches the front of the eye... causes opacity" (R11) • "No, but it can cause a lot of pain" (R10) • "Destroys the battery power behind the eyes" (R9)
D. Participants' knowledge about TT treatments	1. Self-treatment options 2. Other treatment options	How participants treat TT at home; other TT treatments known	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Locally improvised forceps called masepata" (R1, R10, R12, etc.) • "Razor blade to trim lashes" (R9,R11,R33) • "Electricity used to burn roots" (R1) • "Hospital epilation every 1-2 months" (R18)

*full quotes available from corresponding author

reported avoiding weddings, religious gatherings, and social events because of tearing, redness, discharge, frequent blinking, and photophobia. One female participant said: "Yes, I felt ashamed. Sometimes children used to run away from me or point me out to others because of my watery and red eyes" (R14). A male participant responded: "No, it was a test from God towards mankind, a disease condition, and I therefore did not feel ashamed of it at all" (R9).

Loss of independence and a burden to the family

Participants reported depending on children to remove offending lashes, inability to drive motorcycles, and reliance on family members for transport, thereby affecting the family members' work. One participant stated: "It caused me a lot of discomfort, watering, and redness, which were persistent. I only get relief when my son removes them for me" (R5). Another said, "I could not drive my motorcycle because I had a feeling of excessive air blowing into my eyes. ... I had to use commercial transport or depend on my son to take me where I needed to go. So I affected his work too" (R19).

Search for a cure and economic implications

Participants tried multiple treatments: self-epilation with fingers or improvised forceps, epilation at hospitals every 1–2 months, razor blade trimming, and pain medications. Many incurred repeated costs. Quotes: "I used medications to relieve pain and discomfort because I did not know how to remove the offending eyelashes" (R3, R4, R22, R23, R24, R25). "I used a razor blade to trim off the offending lashes" (R9, R11, R33). "I used to go to the hospital where the offending lashes would be shaved off or removed every 1–2 months, and I would sometimes use medications, which I had to pay for repeatedly" (R7, R8, R18).

Interference with family care

Female participants noted that cooking with firewood worsened tearing and discomfort, interfering with their ability to care for families. "It caused tearing in my eyes, which used to be worsened while cooking food for my family, interfering with my ability to take care of my family" (R2, R3, R5).

Effect on sleep

Most participants reported symptoms only when awake, but some removed lashes to sleep well. "I had no problem while sleeping ... the problems usually occurred when I was awake" (R1, R9). "Yes, I used to remove it so that I could sleep well at night" (R13, R17, R22).

B. Participants' experiences following trichiasis surgery

All participants reported improvement.

Improved

Physical symptoms resolved or markedly

improved. "The surgery stopped the eye pains and tearing ... I am very comfortable now" (R1). "I am fine now; all my eye problems of tearing have resolved" (R12). "I feel well now; I don't have to repeatedly remove offending eyelashes anymore" (R6). Even participants without pre-operative discomfort noticed vision improvement: "Though I did not know that I had trichiasis, I was uncomfortable and had blurred vision then but all that has resolved after the surgery" (R16, R21).

Improved independence, security, and earning ability

Participants could travel without fear, no longer needed to carry epilation forceps, and could drive motorcycles. "I used to take my forceps with me wherever I went, but now I am well and can travel freely" (R8, R19). "I can now travel on my motorcycle for long distances without any issues" (R7, R8, R19). Participants felt secure attending social gatherings. Better ability to function and care for family "I used to have tearing and poor vision ... which worsened when cooking, but [it] has now stopped. I am very grateful that I can do my domestic chores freely now" (R3).

C. Participants' knowledge about trichiasis

Causes

Some had correct knowledge: "It is a disease contracted by sharing eye pencils with infected people" (R3). Others had incorrect perceptions: dust/cement exposure (R8), eye scratching (R10, R11), harmattan dust/cold (R1, R5). Many had no idea. Participants were educated after the FGD.

Blindness

Most knew trichiasis could cause blindness, but few knew the mechanism. "Yes, because it scratches the front of the eye and can lead to blindness by causing opacity" (R11). "Yes, my grandmother became blind from it, but I don't know how" (R12). "No, but it can cause a lot of pain and discomfort" (R10). One participant used a local metaphor: "Yes, because it keeps pricking the eyeballs and eventually destroys the battery power behind the eyes" (R9). Education was provided after the discussion.

D. Participants' knowledge about other treatment options

Treatments mentioned included: local epilation with improvised forceps (*masepata*), hospital epilation, electrolysis, razor blade trimming, traditional eye pencils, and pain medications. Many did not know that trimming lashes makes them more abrasive. "I used a locally improvised forceps called *masepata* ... to remove offending lashes every few weeks" (R1, R10, R12, R15, R17, R22, R23, R24, R25). "I also had a procedure in a hospital where electricity was used to burn the roots ... but its effect did not last long" (R1).

Discussion

Trichiasis had a significant negative impact on the quality of life of FGD participants, most of whom were females.¹⁵ Physical symptoms (foreign body sensation, tearing, redness, pain described as “like a knife cutting the eyeball”) caused substantial discomfort, interfering with daily functions, productivity, and sleep. These findings agree with previous studies.^{4,6,8,11,12}

Most participants tried multiple treatments, incurring economic costs and loss of independence, consistent with other reports.^{7,8} Psychological and social health were affected, especially among females who felt embarrassed and avoided social gatherings. Some studies found similar results [7,15,16], while others reported no impact on social health.⁴ The marked gender difference in stigmatisation – females reporting shame and social avoidance, males viewing trichiasis as a divine trial – reflects local cultural and religious frameworks. In the predominantly Hausa-Muslim setting of Bauchi, illness may be interpreted as God’s will (*jarabawa*), potentially reducing psychological distress for men while women face greater social scrutiny over physical appearance. This aligns with studies from Niger⁷ and Ethiopia⁶ and underscores the need for gender-sensitive interventions.

Following surgery, participants reported resolution or marked improvement in physical symptoms, leading to greater independence, improved ability to work, better care for family members, and overall quality of life, including vision.^{6,12,16}

Importantly, even before causing blindness, trichiasis significantly affects multiple health domains. Policies on trachomatous trichiasis elimination are often based only on blindness levels,¹⁷ thereby underestimating the true burden. In the companion quantitative study, <5% of TT patients were blind [16]; nonetheless, HRQoL scores were significantly lower than those of controls and improved after surgery. This qualitative study adds depth to those findings.

Some participants had accurate knowledge of the causes of blindness, while others did not; post-FGD education addressed this. An interesting finding was that participants with incomplete surgical correction still reported significant improvement, and those unaware of their trichiasis noted vision improvement after surgery. This suggests that even partial success can yield meaningful patient-reported benefits.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, all FGDs were conducted after surgery; therefore, pre-surgery experiences were recalled

retrospectively, introducing recall bias and the possibility of “rosy retrospection” (minimising past suffering because of current relief). Future studies should conduct pre-surgery and post-surgery FGDs with the same participants. Second, we did not return transcripts to participants for verification (“member checking”) nor conduct repeat FGDs to confirm interpretations. This reduces credibility according to standard qualitative criteria; however, the use of two independent coders, consensus dialogue, and triangulation with quantitative data [16] partially addresses interpretive validity. Third, gender-mixed FGDs may have inhibited open discussion of stigmatisation, especially for female participants; separate groups would be preferable. Fourth, the use of TT finders for purposive sampling may have introduced response bias. Fifth, the single-region setting limits generalisability. Sixth, potential translation loss and social desirability bias are inherent to FGD research.

Strengths

The qualitative approach provides in-depth knowledge of participants’ lived experiences with trichiasis, which quantitative measures cannot capture. Rich participant quotes vividly illustrate the suffering and the transformative impact of surgery.

Future research

In-depth interviews or narrative research could yield even more detailed accounts of individual experiences. Studies should also examine whether the time interval between surgery and interview affects reported outcomes.

Conclusion

Trachomatous trichiasis had a significant negative impact on participants’ quality of life in this study, affecting physical and social health, daily activities, family care, security, and independence, and leading to prolonged searches for a cure with economic consequences. Trichiasis surgery led to improvements in health, security, independence, ability to work and earn a living, and ability to care for families. Programmes aimed at global trachoma elimination should include assessment of quality-of-life impact alongside clinical outcomes.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the staff and management of the National Eye Centre, Kaduna, for ethical approval; Health and Development Support Program (HANDS) for their cooperation during the free surgical outreach; and the Department of Ophthalmology, Federal University

of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare (FUHSTHA), Bauchi State.

References

- Romani L, Marks M, Sokana O, et al. Feasibility and safety of mass drug co-administration with azithromycin and ivermectin for the control of neglected tropical diseases: a single-arm intervention trial. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2018; 6(10): e1132–e1138.
- Habtamu E, Harding-Esch EM, Greenland K, et al. Trachoma. *Lancet*. 2025; 405(10492): 1865–1878.
- Solomon AW, Burton MJ, Gower EW, et al. Trachoma. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*. 2022;8(1):32.
- Dhaliwal U, Nagpal G, Bhatia MS. Health-related quality of life in patients with trichomatous trichiasis or entropion. *Ophthalmic Epidemiol*. 2006; 13(1): 59–66.
- Shrestha R, Merbs SL, Bayissasse B, et al. Characteristics and perspectives of patients with postoperative trichiasis in Hadiya Zone, Ethiopia. *Int Health*. 2022;14(Suppl 1):i49–i56.
- Habtamu E, Wondie T, Aweke S, et al. Impact of trichiasis surgery on quality of life: a longitudinal study in Ethiopia. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2016; 10(4): e0004627.
- Palmer SL, Winskell K, Patterson AE, et al. 'A living death': a qualitative assessment of quality of life among women with trichiasis in rural Niger. *Int Health*. 2014; 6(4): 291–297.
- Wolle MA, Cassard SD, Gower EW, et al. Impact of trichiasis surgery on physical functioning in Ethiopian patients: STAR trial. *Am J Ophthalmol*. 2011; 151 :850–857.
- Kreis AJ, Gower EW, Kropp M, et al. The prevention and management of postoperative trichomatous trichiasis: a systematic review. *Surv Ophthalmol*. 2024; 69(1): 93–102.
- Burton M, Habtamu E, Ho D, Gower EW. Interventions for trachoma trichiasis. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2015; (11): CD004008.
- Oktavec KC, Cassard SD, Harding JC, et al. Patients' perceptions of trichiasis surgery: results from the Partnership for Rapid Elimination of Trachoma (PRET) Surgery Clinical Trial. *Ophthalmic Epidemiol*. 2015; 22(3): 153–161.
- Habtamu E, Wondie T, Aweke S, et al. Impact of trichiasis surgery on daily living: a longitudinal study in Ethiopia. *Wellcome Open Res*. 2017; 2: 69.
- Mpyet C, Muhammad N, Adamu MD, et al. Prevalence of trachoma in Bauchi State, Nigeria: results of 20 local government area-level surveys. *Ophthalmic Epidemiol*. 2016; 23(sup1): 39–45.
- Im D, Pyo J, Lee H, et al. Qualitative research in healthcare: data analysis. *J Prev Med Public Health*. 2023; 56(2): 100–110.
- Cromwell EA, Courtright P, King JD, et al. The excess burden of trichomatous trichiasis in women: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg*. 2009; 103(10): 985–992.
- Batah H, Wali AH, Umar MM, Oyediji FJ. Impact of trichiasis surgery on health-related quality of life of patients with trichomatous trichiasis in Bauchi Metropolis, North-east Nigeria: a comparative study. *Niger J Ophthalmol*. 2025; 33(3): 130–136.
- GBD 2019 Blindness and Vision Impairment Collaborators. Global estimates of the number of people with blindness and vision impairment due to trachoma, 1990–2019. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2021; 9(2): e144–e160.
- Tanywe AC, Green H, Fernandez R. Perceptions and practices of community members relating to trachoma in Africa: a qualitative systematic review. *JBI Evid Synth*. 2022; 20(10): 2445–2474.
- Njomo DW, Karimurio J, Odhiambo GO, et al. Knowledge, practices and perceptions of trachoma and its control among communities of Narok County, Kenya. *Trop Dis Travel Med Vaccines*. 2016; 2: 13.